

Book of Jeremiah

By Ryan Schroeder, University of British Columbia

Entry tags: Canonical texts, Levantine Religion, Biblical Prophets, Early Jewish Literature, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Ancient Mediterranean, Text, Israelite Religion, Near East, Scripture, Prophecy, Jewish Traditions, Judeans and Israelites, Divination, Ancient Western Asia, Oracle, Hebrew Bible, Jewish Court Tales, Rewriting/Rewritten Bible, Divination, Greek, Septuagint, Language, Ancient Semitic Text, Poetry, Interpretation of text, Semitic, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, West Semitic, Canaanite, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Biblical Hebrew, Central Semitic

The book of Jeremiah presents a collection of poetic oracles uttered by the 7th-6th century prophet Jeremiah, primarily in the kingdom of Judah. The book has a complex literary history, however, and it is clear that Jeremiah himself did not produce the book as a whole. At least two different versions of the book existed in antiquity, one of which was translated into Greek during the Second Temple period. Although the book consists of poetic oracles predominately, there are also narrative texts scattered throughout. In general, the material relates to the fall of Judah/Jerusalem to the Babylonians in the early 6th century BCE, an event that Jeremiah understands to be divine punishment from the god Yahweh.

Date Range: 620 BCE - 200 CE

Region: West Asia

Region tags: Middle East, Israel, West Asia, Egypt, Palestine

The book of Jeremiah was mostly produced in or around Jerusalem, the capital of the Iron Age kingdom of Judah. The book contains some narratives that are set in Egypt, and they may have been written there.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schenker, Adrian, Karl Elliger, Wilhelm Rudolph, and Hans Bardtke. *Biblia hebraica Stuttgartensia*. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1997.
- Source 2: Coogan, Michael D., ed. *The New Oxford Annotated Bible. Fully Revised Fifth Edition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.
- Source 3: Berlin, Adele, and Marc Zvi Brettler, eds. *The Jewish Study Bible*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003.

Notes: The Book of Jeremiah appears translation in all Jewish and Christian Bibles. Fragments of the book in Hebrew and Greek also appear among the Dead Sea Scrolls.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/bible/>

– Source 1 Description: The Society of Biblical Literature outreach website (Bible Odyssey) includes a translation of the Bible that includes Jeremiah.

Notes: The Book of Jeremiah can be readily found in many translations online. Recommended translations include the Jewish Publication Society translation and New Revised Standard Version.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Notes: In addition to papyrus, parchment (i.e., processed goat/sheep skin) was a writing surface used for preserving the text of the book of Jeremiah.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: There was apparently a complex and lengthy process of composition and revision that took place at both pre- and post-written stages of the book's creation.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– I don't know

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No
- ↳ Temple
 - Yes
- ↳ Shrine
 - I don't know
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - Yes
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– I don't know

Notes: Manuscripts of the book of Jeremiah were possibly kept by private individuals.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Early portions thereof may have been housed within the palace.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

Notes: While prophets are/were not necessarily considered "divine or semi-divine," they are/were thought to possess a unique relationship with a deities.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: While prophets are/were considered "non-divine" human beings, they are/were thought to possess a unique relationship with a deities.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: Especially during the early period of the specified dates (620 BCE - 200 CE), the book of Jeremiah underwent a number of major revisions. After this period, however, the text came to assume two relatively stable textual forms (one form preserved in the Greek language and the other preserved in Hebrew language).

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Notes: While there is no official canon list during this period (620 BCE–200 CE), hierarchies of religiously/culturally authoritative texts did emerge by the end of this period. The book of Jeremiah was among the "Prophets," a loosely defined category of texts that came to be venerated by Judaeans/Jewish cultural and religious elites during this period.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Notes: Note that the "political," "social," and "cultural" were in many respects indistinguishable from the "religious" in antiquity.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– I don't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– Yes

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– I don't know

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– I don't know

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– I don't know

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– I don't know

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– I don't know

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to discern any differences in the status of the various early versions of the book of Jeremiah. At least two distinct versions appear among the Dead Sea Scrolls; evidently both versions were accepted within early Second Temple Judaism. Eventually, the version associated with the Greek language was adopted primarily by Christians, while the version associated with the Hebrew language was adopted within the rabbinic tradition.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– I don't know

Notes: While later religious communities may debate the proper version, there is no indication that this was a concern within the first few centuries of the book's existence.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Usage, presence among other authoritative texts, and association with famous prophets of the past.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: The notion of a biblical "canon" came into existence slowly and overlapped with the time period during which the book of Jeremiah took shape.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The book of Jeremiah likely played a role in scribal training.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The book of Jeremiah is presented as a collection of oracles (or "prophecies") uttered by the priest/prophet Jeremiah. It also contains a number of narratives about Jeremiah.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The book of Jeremiah refers to the priestly lineage of its namesake, as well as royal lineages in the kingdom of Judah and neighbouring countries.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– No

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The book of Jeremiah does not contain any legislation, but it does allude to pentateuchal and/or related legal texts and customs.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: See Jeremiah 22:18-19.

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– I don't know

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– I don't know

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– I don't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– I don't know

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– I don't know

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– I don't know

↳ In cemetery?

– I don't know

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: N/A

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– I don't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - No
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– Yes

↳ Can be hurt?
– I don't know

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– I don't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– I don't know

↳ In dreams?
– Yes

↳ In trance possession?
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch?
– No

↳ Other?
–Specify: N/A

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– No

Are other categories of beings present?
– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?
– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)
– No

↳ Divination through human communication?
– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?
– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other form of divination:

– Specify: Bibliomancy/divinatory exegesis.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: While the deity Yahweh appears throughout the Hebrew Bible and in inscriptional evidence. However, the responses in this section are based on the presentation of Yahweh in the Book of Jeremiah, specifically, rather than on a composite image of the deity based on the various sources that exist.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Sacred objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: The deity Yahweh expected the people of Judah to venerate him alone (see, e.g., Jeremiah 7:16-20; 44:1-30)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - No
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - Yes

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - No
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes

|

- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The term "eschaton" may be too all-encompassing for the Book of Jeremiah, which has in view the restoration of the fortunes of the people of Judah, rather than a resolution to the "world" history per se. The central idea is that the people of Judah are being punished for their sins (acts against other humans and against the deity), but the kingdom will be restored in the future.

- ↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
 - No
- ↳ At specified time in future
 - Yes
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– Yes

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Field doesn't know

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– No

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
 - Notes: Fidelity to the deity.
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No

- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Monogamy (males)

– Field doesn't know

Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?
– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?
– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?
– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– Yes

↳ Drama?
– Yes

↳ Comedy?
– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A nation-state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The production and reproduction of literary texts such as the Book of Jeremiah was controlled by scribal experts, typically associated with the palace and/or temple.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: See Jeremiah 36:9-32.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: While the book of Jeremiah contains no formal legal material, it does explicitly advocate for cultic reform and alludes to customs aimed at protecting marginalized members of society (see, e.g., Jer 7:1-7).

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

- ↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?
– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Book of Jeremiah, Najman, Hindy, and Konrad Schmid, eds.. *Jeremiah's Scriptures Production, Reception, Interaction, and Transformation*. Edited by Hindy Najman and Konrad Schmid. *Supplements to the Journal for the Study of Judaism*. Leiden: Brill, 2017.

Reference: Book of Jeremiah, King, Philip J.. *Jeremiah: An Archaeological Companion*. Louisville: Westminster/John Knox Press, 1993.

Reference: Book of Jeremiah, Tov, Emanuel. "The Literary History of the Book of Jeremiah in Light of Its Textual History". In *Empirical Model for Biblical Criticism*, edited by Jeffrey H. Tigay, 213–37. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1985.

Reference: Book of Jeremiah, Dempsey, Carol J.. "The Oxford Handbook of Jeremiah. Edited by Louis Stulman and Edward Silver. New York: Oxford University Press, 2021. V + 683. \$150.00." 49, no. 2 (December 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1017/hor.2022.59>.

Reference: Book of Jeremiah, Leuchter, Mark. *Jeremiah*. Edited by Carolyn J. Sharp. Oxford University Press, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199859559.013.10>.